

MEDICAL SCIENCES

RESULTS OF COMPLEX APPLICATION OF MECHANICAL AND DRUG REVASCULARIZATION AND SEPARATELY PERFORMED PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION IN ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WORKING IN ENVIRONMENTALLY UNFAVORABLE CONDITIONS CONTAMINATED WITH XENOBIOTICS

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the integrated use of propranolol with heparin and percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI); propranolol with tenecteplase, syto-mask in combination with PCI and separately only PCI for hemodynamics, cardiohemodynamics and the clinical course in the acute period, as well as in the observation of MI. The results of complex drug and mechanical revascularization are compared.

Materials and research methods. 63 patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS) were examined: myocardial infarction non elevation ST segment, at the age from 30 to 70 years (56.7 ± 1.20), which were divided into 3 groups of 21 people by randomization. In the 1st group, they were treated with heparin, propranolol with Cito-Mak, kardiotekst, preduktal MR35mq, BLAII and PCI; in the 2nd group, methylase (tenecteplase) and propranolol were administered, fozinopril was given, and PCI was performed after 24 hours; in the 3rd group only PCI was produced. Using echocardiography and Doppler echocardiography, the values the end systolic volume (ESV), end diastolic volume (EDV), ejection fraction (EF), stroke index (SI), cardiac index (CI), and the index of the disturbance of local left ventricular contractility (LVC) and also established the dynamics of systolic and diastolic blood pressure, the clinical course of OKMI in the observation period.

Results and discussion. Administration of heparin, propranolol kardiotekst, Cito- Mak infusion, preduktal MR35 mq and AIIbl oral administration and transdermal coronary intervention (PCI) administration after 24 hours accelerate stabilization of central hemodynamics. The reduced ESV, EDV, IALC and decreased, degree improves left ventricular systolic function, increases PV. There was no restenosis, recurrence of MI and mortality. In one patient, on 5 days, was recorded DOS.

During treatment with fozinopril, propranolol with heparin and PCI, central hemodynamics are systolic function (group 1). At the same time, in 2 patients, on day 3 and 3, was recorded DOS, in 1 - recurrence of MI. When only PCI was performed, 4 patients developed recurrence of MI, 4 had restenosis, 2 had AHF, and 2 died.

Conclusions. The result of this work shows that the integrated use of drug therapy with percutaneous coronary intervention allows you to get a prognostically positive result in contrast to using only PCI.

Keywords: ACS- myocardial infarction, heparin, methylase (tenecteplase), Cyto- Mac, fozinopril, propranolol, kardiotekst, drug therapy, PCI, Preduktal MR35, central hemodynamics, cardiohemodynamics, medium molecules of peptides -SMP, angiotensin-2 receptor blockers (brAII, clinical course.

In recent years, the process of interaction between the human body and environmental factors has been modeled, practical aspects of assessing the anthropogenic influence of environmental factors and methods for assessing human health have been studied. Among these aspects, the leading place is occupied by both the protection of the human habitat and the problems of ecology of the internal environment of the human body.

The development of industry and agricultural technology increases environmental pollution - soil, air, water, food, electromagnetic radiation and others contribute to the development of environmental degradation. Environmental degradation is the result of growing ecological exotoxicosis. In some cases, environmental exotoxicosis contributes to the expansion and deepening of morbidity and mortality. According to WHO, currently, a significant part of diseases are derived from the effects of anthropogenic factors (H_2SO_4 , H_2S , SO_2 , CO , CO_2 , NO , NO_2 , petroleum carbonic anhydrates, resins, electromagnetic radiation, etc.) on the human body, causing chronic poisoning, which contribute to an increase in the average peptide

molecules (SMP) (1, 5, 6, 9). The level of average peptide molecules is a test that characterizes the severity of endotoxicosis (5,7, 10), which increases the impact of risk factors for coronary heart disease - ACS. Increases myocardial hypoxia, reduces tissue resistance, worsens blood rheology, disrupts microcirculation. All this in total causes the expansion of the hypoxia -ischemia - necrosis zone (1,6,10), which contributes to the development of heart failure (HF), violation of the electrical stability of the myocardium - rhythm disturbances (HP) and sudden coronary death (VS) in the period of inpatient rehabilitation of ACS BP ST (1,2,4,6,8,10). The failure of ACS treatment often depends on an insufficient assessment of the severity of environmental exo- and endotoxicosis associated with massive intake of catabolism products from the necrosis focus and xenobiotics into the bloodstream [1,7]. In this regard, new methods of exposure are currently being sought, leading to a decrease in ecoendotoxicosis (1, 4,10), preventing or reducing the development of various complications in ACS (3,4).

Table 1.

Characteristics of patients working in environmentally unfavorable conditions.

Contaminated with xenobiotics are environmentally unfavorable conditions (n =63)	Heparin+propranolol+ CytoMac+cardiotext+preductal MR 35mg+brA II and PCI (n=21)		Methylase+propranolol+cyto-mac + +PCI (n=21)		PCI (n=21)	
	Number of patients (n=21)	Work experience (years)	Number of patients (n=21)	Work experience (years)	Number of patients (n=21)	Work experience (years)
Motor transport park	4	15,21+ 2,20	4	22,13+ 1,20	5	18,20+ 2,30
Oil and gas producing plants	4	16,30+ 3,00	4	15,90+ 2,5	3	15,90+ 3,10
Oil and gas producing plants	4	20,10+ 1,4	3	16,31+ 2,2	4	16,30 + 4,60
Chemical plants	3	16,25 + 3,15	3	17,30+ 3,1	2	17,40+ 2,30
Electrotherm Plant	2	14,56 + 2,90	2	15,11+ 2,21	3	17,20 + 2,20
Synthetic Rubber Plant	1	10,20+ 2,35	2	13,12+ 2,2	2	10,23 + 2,10
Cement Plant	1	12,31+ 2,20		11,80+ 3,00		
Stone quarry						
Factory of rubber products, etc.	2	14,49 + 3,00	3	10,33+ 2,34	2	15,50+ 2,30
Time of hospitalization	1 -5 yaca	—	-5 yaca	1-5 yaca	—	1 -5 yaca

The material was statistically processed using the "Statistics 6.0" software package, the values of M, standard errors (m) and a 95% reliable interval were calculated. At the same time, the nonparametric Mann-Whitney criterion, the exact criterion of R. Fischer were used. The differences were considered significant at <0.05 .

Research results

Indicators of ADs, ADd, SI, UI, heart rate both in the group treated with heparin with propranolol, Cyto-Mac + cardiotext + preductal MR35, brAII and PCI (group 1), Methylase (tenecteplase) with fosinopril and propranolol, cyto-mac in combination with PCI, and separately PCI with admission of patients to the hospital was approximately equal ($p>0.05$; see table.) At the same time, hyper- and eukinetic variants of hemodynamics were mainly observed in all patients.

Against the background of administration of heparin with propranolol, Cyto-Maca + cardiotext, oral administration of preductal MR 35mg, BLAIII and PCI, a decrease in ADp was noted after 12 hours and until the end of the study from 138.4 ± 2.2 to 121.8 ± 1.8 mmHg. However, no significant decrease was observed compared to the initial values of ADp ($p>0.05$; table 2). In this group, 3 patients with initially low blood pressure had a tendency to increase it (before treatment 110/60, after - 125/65 mmHg). In 5 patients, the blood pressure level did not change significantly.

With the introduction of methylase, propranolol, Cyto-Mac and ingestion of fosinopril and PCI after a day, the ADs almost stabilized: after 24 hours it was already 118.0 ± 2.2 mmHg, and by the end of observation - 120.2 ± 2.3 mmHg. At the same time, the ADd gradually decreased on the 7th day treatment was 80.20 ± 1.4 mmHg. However, these indicators did not significantly differ from group 1 ($p>0.05$; see Table 2).

The dynamics of changes in the indicators of central hemodynamics on the days of treatment is presented in the table ($p> 0.05$).

In group 1 patients, there was no significant decrease in MI and SI. After a day, they increased and at the end of the study amounted to 61.3 ± 1.8 ml/m² ($p<0.01$) and 4.8 ± 1.3 l/min/m², respectively ($p=0.05$; see table). In patients of group 2, after 12 hours, decreases in MI and SI were not recorded, on the contrary, they increased (from 39.9 ± 0.3 ml/m² to 58.9 ± 1.6

ml/m² and from 3.92 ± 0.03 l/min/m² to 4.95 ± 0.08 l/min/m²) and significantly differed from the baseline level ($p<0.01$; see table2). Subsequently, the values of UI and SI in the 1st and 2nd groups did not differ ($p>0.05$; see the table). A separate analysis of SI indicators revealed that in the 1st group receiving heparin with propranolol, Cyto-Mac + cardiotext, oral administration of preductal MR35mg, BLAIII and PCI in 9 patients SI increased from 3.00l/min/ m² to 4.98-, in 8 - from 3.25- to 4.99l/min/m², in 4 - from 3.64 to 4.93 l/min/m² and significantly differed from the data of the 2nd group ($p>0.01$; see table).

In group 2 patients treated with methylase (tenecteplase), Cyto-Mac, propranolol with fosinopril in combination with PCI, in 6 patients, SI increased from 3.00l/min/m² to 4.90-, in 7 - from 3.25- to 3.95-, in 7 - from 4, 89 -to 4,10 l/min/m², in 5 - from 3.72 to 4.87 l/min/m², no significant changes were observed in two patients (from 3.6 to 3.9 l/min/m²).

A significant decrease in heart rate in group 1 patients was observed after 24 hours - from 100.0 ± 3.10 to 75.0 ± 2.1 beats/min and remained until the end of the study. In patients of group 2, the heart rate decreased from 98.6 ± 3.10 to 85.5 ± 1.6 beats/min (see Table 2).

Changes in indicators characterizing LV functions during the study are presented in Table 2. In our study, the initial indicators of LV functions did not differ significantly ($p>0.05$; seetable 2).

The BDO with the introduction of heparin, infusion of propranolol, Cyto-Mac, cardiotext, oral administration of MR 35mg, brAII and PCI during observation and treatment decreased. After 12 hours of the disease, it progressively decreased and statistically significantly differed from the indicator before treatment with STEMI. With the introduction of tenecteplase, Cyto-Maca, infusion of propranolol, ingestion of fosinopril together with PCI, a decrease in BWW was also recorded. However, the value of this indicator did not significantly differ from that obtained in group 1 ($p>0.05$). In group 3 patients who were treated only with PCI, there was also a tendency to decrease in BWW (see table): the values of these data significantly differed from the results obtained in the 1st and 2nd groups.

Table 2

Indicators	Indicators of central hemodynamics, LV systolic function and clinical course (M±m)														P ₁
	Heparin, propranolol + cyto-mac +cardiotest+ preductal MR 35 +BLAI+ PCI (n=21)							Tenecteplase+ propranolol + cyto-mac+ fosinopril + PCI (n=21)							
	Время, прошедшее от начала лечения														
	Before treatment	12 ч	24 ч	72 ч	7 день	До лечения	12 ч	24 ч	72 ч	7 день	До лечения	12 ч	24 ч	72 ч	7 день
ADs, mmHg	138,0±2,3 P>0,05	123,0±2,3	126,0±1,6	125,2±1,6	118,8±1,8	138,4±2,2 P>0,05	125,5±2,1	118,0±2,2	121,0±3,7	120,2±2,3	142,4±2,2 P>0,05	135,2±1,6	127,8±3,4	125,5±2,2	125,5±1,8
ADd, mmHg.	86,7±1,3 P>0,05	78,7±1,7	73,7±1,6	65,1±3,3	75,9±3,2	87,9±1,2 P>0,05	87,6±1,4	82,6±1,4	80,0±1,3	80,2±1,4	85,9±1,2 P>0,05	75,0±1,0	74,00±2,40	72,4±1,3	65,1±1,6
SMP usl. ed.	6,00±0,28 P>0,05	4,63±0,30	3,44±0,10	0,30±0,11	0,28±0,02 P>0,05	6,2±0,06 P>0,05	3,86±0,13	3,80±0,16	3,25±0,12	0,24±0,11	6,10±0,15 P>0,05	5,42±0,20	4,63±0,15	4,38±0,26	4,22±0,20
UI, ml/m2	38,00±1,4	40,5±1,9	39,6±2,0	44,5±1,6	58,9±16	39,9±0,3	39,9±0,2	40,7±1,1	42,5±1,2	61,3±1,8	39,9±0,3	40,8±1,4	41,86±1,14	40,8±1,4	48,5±1,6
SI, l/min/m2	3,92±0,03	2,90±0,08	3,0±0,07	4,80±0,13	4,93±1,3	3,92±0,03	4,40±0,04	4,90±0,12	4,95±0,1657	4,95±0,18	3,82±0,03	3,98±0,12	3,98±0,17	3,98±0,12	3,98±0,17
qSS, ud/min	100±3,10 P>0,05	88,6±2,8	75,00±2,1	75,72±2,1	75,0±2,0	98,6±3,10 P>0,05	95,5±2,2	96,3±1,9	84,32±2,1	75,50±1,6	100,0±2,4 P>0,05	98,50±1,6	96,20±1,9	86,32±2,1	78,14±1,9
CSR, ml	90,20±2,90 P>0,05	70,23±2,31	65,90±2,42	53,2±2,61	51,34±2,61	90,32±2,6 P>0,05	68,25±2,31	60,90±2,42	51,34±2,61	50,23±2,5	89,33±3,4 P>0,05	87,50±1,6	88,23±2,3	78,20±2,1	67,10±2,4
KDO, ml	165,10±2,90 P>0,05	150,11±2,29	143,71±2,15	135,82±2,17	135,82±2,17	164,18±2,00 P>0,05	146,27±2,11	142,32±2,19	134,31±2,22	131,7±2,13	164,18±2,00 P>0,05	159,82±2,16	155,92±2,12	151,82±2,16	148,92±2,12
FW, %	45,69±2,5 P>0,05	50,21±2,2	51,34±2,61	58,24±2,17	59,31±2,14	46,80±2,30 P>0,05	52,30±2,11	55,12±1,90	59,32±2,13	61,4±2,17	45,90±2,10 P>0,05	45,73±1,61	48,82±1,53	50,71±1,47	55,31±2,14
INLS	1,81±0,10 P>0,05	1,48±0,23	1,35±0,30	0,81±0,17	0,82±0,14	1,78±0,19 P>0,05	1,45±0,17	1,31±0,15	0,82±0,14	0,80±0,12	1,78±0,16 P>0,05	1,65±0,21	1,58±0,15	1,29±0,14	0,99±0,12
Restenosis 0								1					3		
Relapse 0								1					2		
OSN 1								1					2		
Lethality 0								0					1		

Note: P is a significant difference in the initial indicators, P1 is a significant difference in the final results between the groups.

In an individual analysis, 98% of group 1 patients and 92% of group 2 patients showed a decrease in LV BWV ($p > 0.05$; see table).

LV CSR in groups 1 and 2 decreased by 44.4 and 43.3%, respectively, ($p > 0.05$; see table).

The initial values of LV as the main indicator of LV systolic function did not differ between the groups ($p > 0.05$; see Table 2). The change in LVEF was considered significant above 45% or below 40%. In group 1, by the end of day 1 and on day 7, the FV increased ($51.34 \pm 2.61\%$ and $59.31 \pm 2.14\%$), and these indicators did not differ from the values in group 2 (55.12 ± 1.9 and $61.4 \pm 2.17\%$). An individual analysis of the indicators revealed an increase in LV LV in 99% of patients of group 1, in 93% of group 2. A decrease in LV contractile function was noted in one patient (4.8%) of group 1, in 3 (14.4%) - in group 2, in 7 (33.3%) patients of group 3.

LV INLS values were different (see the table). As a quantitative indicator, violation of local LV contractility has prognostic value in ACS pd ST. Due to a significant decrease in the volume of the lesion, the degree of myocardial asinergia in patients of group 1, LV INLS decreased (before treatment 1.81 ± 0.10 , at the end of treatment 0.82 ± 0.14). The introduction of tenecteplase and infusion of propranolol, Cyto-Maca, oral administration of fasinopril in combination with PCI contributed to a decrease in LV INLS from 1.78 ± 0.13 to 0.98 ± 0.12 . The data significantly differed from the 1st group. In group 1, 95% of patients, in group 2 - 91% of patients, in group 3 - 45% had a significant decrease in LV INLS.

There were no significant differences in the clinical condition of patients on day 1. The combined use of heparin with propranolol, Cyto - Maca, cardiotext, oral administration of MR 35mg, brAII and PCI, as well as the introduction of tenecteplase and infusion of propranolol, taking fasinopril in combination with PCI prevented the development of LV functional inferiority and led to a decrease in the frequency of other complications of STEMI. So, if before the study anginal pain was observed in group 1 in 7 (33.3%), in group 2 - in 20 (95.2%) patients, then against the background of the therapy, the pain disappeared in 21 (100%) and 18 (90%) patients, respectively. The frequency of postinfarction angina in group 1 was not observed, in group 2 it was 5%, 8% - in group 3.

Recurrent course of ACS BST, restenosis, relapse, mortality were not observed in group 1. One patient developed OSN on the 7th day. In group 2, one patient had OSN, another relapsed, and the third patient developed restenosis. In group 3, OSN was registered in 2 patients on day 3, restenosis in 2, relapse in 3, and one patient died. Mortality was not observed in groups 1 and 2.

Thus, recanalization of the coronary arteries with the combined use of heparin with propranolol, Cyto-Poppy, cardiotext, oral administration of MR 35mg, brAII and PCI (group 1), as well as the introduction of tenecteplase, Cyto-Poppy and propranolol infusion, taking fasinopril plus PCI (group 2) contributed to a decrease in SMP, CSR, BWT, INLS and an increase in

LV LV in the acute period of ACS bp ST. Hemodynamic parameters were stabilized, without leading to a critical decrease in blood pressure. In group 1, the development of coronary artery restenosis, recurrence of MI and mortality were prevented. However, in the 2nd group, coronary artery restenosis was recorded, a relapse of ST.

Discussion

Recently, it has been recognized that the prevention of complications and improvement of the prognosis of ACS is an urgent problem of cardiology. As is known, with ACS BP ST, the volume of the lesion begins to increase from the first hour, the systolic and diastolic functions of the LV are disrupted, which contributes to the development of various complications, especially cardiogenic shock, heart failure, electrical instability of the myocardium, remodeling of the heart and leads to mortality. Treatment with thrombolytic drugs is often accompanied by arrhythmia and reperfusion syndrome, every third patient develops a relapse (18, 21).

Separately performed PCI, as an alternative to coronary bypass surgery in the treatment of ACS, is widely used as an effective and safe method of therapy. However, restenosis of the coronary arteries is the main limitation of the effectiveness of this method (4, 10, 11, 19).

In this regard, the search for new drugs and methods to prevent these complications and improve the prognosis of ACS, in particular OCSbp, remains an urgent task (3, 4, 8, 19, 20). In recent years, much attention has been paid to the use of medical and mechanical reperfusion in the acute period of MI (2, 3, 4, 18, 19). However, there is no consensus on their combined use. There is evidence that standard PCI, performed immediately after successful thrombolysis, increases the frequency of complications such as OSN, restenosis, recurrence of ACS (2, 11, 21). After drug reperfusion, remodeling of residual stenosis of the infarct-related artery continues from next week (4, 5, 9, 1, 9). Restoration of coronary blood flow with the help of medications (anticoagulants, antiplatelet agents, thrombolytics, angiotensin AII receptor blockers, beta-blockers, propranolol, Cito - Maca, cardiotext, oral administration of MR 35mg, brAII (losartan), PCI and separate mechanical revascularization contribute not only to the revival of the local kinetics of segments with dormant myocardium in the ischemic and periinfarction zone, but also to a decrease in CSR, CDR, INLS and an increase in the total LV of the left ventricle.

Separately performed PCI as an alternative to coronary bypass surgery in the treatment of ACS in the acute period is widely used as an effective and safe method of therapy. However, restenosis of the coronary arteries is the main limitation of the effectiveness of this method (4, 8, 12, 18, 20).

The available clinical data (5), as well as the results of our studies (2) show that the use of beta-blockers, in particular propranolol, metoprolol succinate, Cyto-Maca, cardiotext, oral administration of MR 35mg, brAII (losartan) before PCI and coronary bypass surgery, it can be considered as an important component of myocardial protection and mortality reduction

in this category of patients (2, 3, 19). However, due to hypotension and negative inotropic and other actions of beta-blockers, they were used only in 20-35% of ACS patients. At the same time, therapy with beta-blockers is associated with a lower incidence of atrial fibrillation in the early period of PCI. But the use of beta-blockers (propranolol, metoprolol succinate) before PCI and coronary bypass surgery, in addition to significantly reducing nonfatal myocardial infarction or nonfatal cardiac arrest, increases the risk of death from other causes and the development of strokes in this group of patients (7, 9, 11, 13, 14). Meanwhile, according to literature data and our experience, taking into account reasonable contraindications, the use of propranolol or metoprolol succinate does not give negative consequences (2, 3, 7, 13). In addition, in recent years, much attention has been paid to the use of ACE inhibitors, brAII (1, 2, 4, 8) in order to prevent the development of post-infarction LV remodeling, HF during the period of ACS observation. Of the last representatives of ACE inhibitors, fosinopril and brAII – losartan are widely used for hypertension and CHF.

As our studies show, heparin, improving the rheological properties of blood, in large doses has a thrombolytic effect (1, 6), increases blood supply in the peri-infarction zone.

Taking into account the above and the lack of data on the combined use of heparin, beta-blockers -propranolol, cyto-maca, cardiotext together with MR35mg preduktal and brAII – (losartan) and PCI, as well as tectoplase therapy and infusion of propranolol, cyto-maca taking ACE inhibitors (fosinopril) with PCI and separate mechanical revascularization of infarct-related arteries in ACS, we conducted a number of studies and received positive results. The combined use of methylase with propranolol together with ACE-fosinopril, heparin and PCI in ACS gives a good therapeutic effect and allows us to consider their use pathogenetically justified to prevent left ventricular dysfunction, relapses and restenosis of the infarct-associated coronary artery in PCI. The positive effect of ACE inhibitors on the processes of LV remodeling of the heart in necrosis and studies on the use of ACE inhibitors in the acute period of MI (ISIS-4-kaptopril; GISSI-lizinopril; AIRE-ramipril, etc.) confirm the expediency of using ACE inhibitors in the critical period of ACS.

However, in ACS, the combined use of heparin, propranolol, cardiotext, cyto-mac, and preuctalmrmg with brAII gives a better clinical result. This allows the use of brAII to reduce myocardial hypertrophy, increase coronary blood flow, improve contractile and pumping function of the myocardium, reduce the risk of recurrent myocardial infarction and sudden death.

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THE INFLUENCE OF EXTRAGENITAL PATHOLOGY OF THE MOTHER ON THE PROCESSES OF FERTILITY AND THE FORMATION OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM OF THE OFFSPRING

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Abstract

The influence of extra genital pathology on the reproductive function of female rats and the structural and functional development of the immune system of the offspring was researched. More pronounced violations of reproductive function were found in females with chronic toxic hepatitis (CTH) than in autoimmune enterocolitis (AIE). The appearance of prenatal mortality in females, an increase in mortality of rat pups on days 1-3 after birth, a lag in the development of offspring, in the form of a decrease in growth and weight indicators, the mass of internal organs of rat pups, were also more pronounced in the group with CTG. Deeper structural and functional changes in early postnatal ontogenesis associated with a lag in the development of the thymus, spleen, mesenteric lymph nodes and Peyer's patches before the transition of rat pups to mixed and definitive nutrition is also characteristic of the offspring of CTG females.

Keywords: hepatitis, enterocolitis, mother, offspring, early postnatal ontogenesis, development, thymus, spleen, mesenteric lymph nodes, Peyer's patches.

It is known that the full development of a newborn directly depends on the state of health of the mother and father during the period of conception, and then completely on the state of the mother during pregnancy and postpartum lactation [13, 14, 25, 27]. However, in recent years, the frequency of various extra genital diseases in women of childbearing age tends to increase. First, this applies to diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, in particular, to lesions of the hepatobiliary system due to viral hepatitis and chronic enterocolitis [1, 3, 8, 19]. It has been established that chronic lesions of the mother's liver cause various changes in hematological parameters, cellular and humoral immunity in the offspring [22]. The consequences of chronic enterocolitis are anemia, hypovitaminosis among women of childbearing age, which naturally have a negative impact on the development of offspring. At the same time, in the literature available to us, information regarding the influence of chronic liver damage and chronic enterocolitis of the mother on the structural foundations of the formation of the organs of immunogens of the offspring could not be found. Meanwhile, the solution of this problem would make it possible to understand the mechanisms of immunodeficiency in children born to mothers with liver damage and chronic enterocolitis and to substantiate the preventive correction and prevention of possible diseases in children.

The purpose of the research was to study the effect of chronic heliothral hepatitis and chronic autoimmune enterocolitis on the reproductive function of female rats and the structural state of the organs of the immune system of their offspring during early postnatal ontogenesis.

Materials and methods

The experiments were carried out on 120 mature female white outbred rats weighing 170-190 g. The animals were divided into 3 groups (40 rats in each): the control group (K), the first experimental group with chronic toxic hepatitis (CTH) and the second experimental group with autoimmune enterocolitis (AIE). The study followed the "Principles for the Care of Laboratory Animals" (NIH Publication No. 85-23, revised 1985). The CTG model was obtained according to the generally accepted method [1], by weekly administration of 0.05 mg of heliothrin per 1 g of animal body weight for 6 weeks. The control group received sterile saline instead of heliothrin.

The tissue antigen for reproducing experimental auto allergic or autoimmune enterocolitis, that is, for the second experimental group, was a homologous, homogenized suspension of the mucous membrane of the large and small intestines on complete Freund's adjuvant. For immunization, 0.5 ml of this antigen was thoroughly mixed with 0.5 ml of warmed complete adjuvant and injected subcutaneously weekly for 6 weeks.